

**Born Compressed:
Should the Preservation Community
Embrace Lossy Video Compression?**

No Time To Wait 3, 25. & 26.10.2018 – David Pfluger

> Content

Point of view of users of audiovisual archives:

„It makes no sense to ‚inflate‘ digital born compressed to uncompressed/losslessly compressed files.

Those files are very cumbersome to handle for researchers who are only interested in the image content.“

Drawing by Shoo Rainer

> Content

(1)

Technical characteristics and access hierarchy
of archival files.

(2)

The use of lossy compression in archival masters.

> Technical characteristics

> Technical characteristics

> Technical characteristics

Source

- „What you get“
- Analogue / Digital
- Any (data) format
- Do not dispose of !
- Contains and comes with metadata

> Technical characteristics

Archival Storage

- Long term digital storage
- Archival file format
- *Digital representation* of source element
- Metainformation is processed and added

> Technical characteristics

Archival Storage

Born digital files are converted into an archival file format which complies with the requirements for archival file formats, to improve its longevity.

Equal to analogue and tape source elements, the digital born file should be kept as received.

> Technical characteristics

Archival Storage - Conditions

„Openness“ / non-proprietary

High level of adoption

Low complexity

High level of documentation (standard)

Robustness to errors

Low dependency on specific hard- and software

No encryption

Drawing by Shoo Rainer

> Technical characteristics

Presentation

- High quality master element
- Any suitable file format
- *Visual representation* of source element
- Contains important information about the visual representation

> Technical characteristics

Viewing

- Low quality element
- Any suitable file format
- Limited visual representation of source element
- Metadata helps to correctly interpret what you see/hear

> Access hierarchy

> Access hierarchy

> Access hierarchy

Search Engine

Presentation

Viewing

M

Archival Storage

M

Source (Digital Born)

Geographically
Separated
2nd Copy

M

Source (Analogue/AV Tape)

M

> Access hierarchy EASY

Search Engine

Presentation

Viewing

M

Archival Storage

M

Source (Digital Born)

Geographically
Separated
2nd Copy

M

Source (Analogue/AV Tape)

M

> Access hierarchy

LIMITED

Presentation

Viewing

M

Archival Storage

M

Source (Digital Born)

Geographically
Separated
2nd Copy

M

Source (Analogue/AV Tape)

M

> Access hierarchy

> Access hierarchy

RESTRICTED

Search Engine

Presentation

Viewing

M

Archival Storage

M

Source (Digital Born)

Geographically
Separated
2nd Copy

M

Source (Analogue/AV Tape)

M

> Access hierarchy

„NONE“

> Conclusion 1

Point of view of users of audiovisual archives:

„It makes no sense to “w up” digital born compressed to compressed/losslessly compressed files.

Those files are very cumbersome to handle for researchers who are only interested in the image content.”

> Conclusion 1

When accessing a digital AV element in an archive researchers should not get in touch with the archival data file format.

For viewing purposes the viewing files are made.

In almost all cases these files should suffice together with the corresponding metadata.

Else the archive you are consulting needs to fix their access hierarchy.

> Topic in need of clarification!

> Topic in need of clarification!

Source

„Rawscan“
Graded Master
Restored Master
etc.

Presentation

Viewing

M

SIP?

AIP?

DIP?

> Content

(2)

The use of lossy compression in archival masters.

MEMORIAV RECOMMENDATIONS

DIGITAL ARCHIVING OF FILM AND VIDEO: PRINCIPLES AND GUIDANCE

Agathe Jarczyk, Reto Kromer, Yves Niederhäuser, David Pfluger

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> Lossy compression

Archival Storage - Conditions

„Openness“ = Non-proprietary

High Level of Adoption

Low Complexity

High Level of Documentation (Standard)

Robustness to Errors

Low Dependency on Specific Hard- and Software

No Encryption

Formats	Data rate	Work area	Suitability for archiving
Apple ProRes	SD: 30–62 Mbit/s HD: 100–250 Mbit/s	Post-production	Not recommended
XDCam HD (MPEG-2)	50 Mbit/s	Recording, post-production	Conditionally recommended
FFV1 (from version 3)	variable	Archive	Recommended
Avid-Codecs (DNxHD)	SD: 146–186 Mbit/s	Post-production	Not recommended
REDCODE RAW family, closely related to JPEG 2000 (HD only)	HD: 224–336 Mbit/s	Recording	Not recommended

> Lossy compression

Art collecting institution

- Mixed collection
- ca. 145 AV artworks
- 135 in SD video, carrier based
(U-Matic, Beta SP, VHS, Laserdisc, DigiBeta, DVD)
- 10 digital born in HD video, lossy compression
- In-house production of documentation in HD video

> Lossy compression

Assumption for the in-house production of documentation:
30% of works are documented with a 60 min HD video.

> Lossy compression

- Uncompressed
- ffV1
- XDCam HD

> Lossy compression

Drawbacks

- Chances that the data is lost is higher for the documenting footage.
- More efforts need to be invested in regular checks for obsolete formats.
- You may have to transcode in a future migration step which may decrease the image quality.

> Conclusion?

> Thanks for your attention!

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